

Basic Values of Russians as a Factor of Their Willingness to Use the Digital Rouble

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the association between basic human values and attitudes towards the digital rouble. It was hypothesised that the values of the categories ‘Self-Enhancement’ and ‘Openness to Change’ (as defined by S.H. Schwartz) would be positively associated with acceptance of the digital rouble. The study was conducted online with 300 participants using Schwartz’s PVQ-R test and a methodology for assessing attitudes towards the digital rouble, which was developed based on the methodology for assessing acceptance of central bank digital currency (Söilen and Benhayoun 2021). The study only partially confirmed the hypotheses. Russians’ acceptance of the digital rouble was positively associated with the higher-order values of ‘Self-Transcendence’ and ‘Self-Enhancement’, while a negative association was found with the ‘Openness to Change’. Based on previous studies, we conclude that the logic behind the associations between values and acceptance of a state-issued digital currency differs from that of a non-state digital currency. The findings suggest that Russians currently do not see the digital rouble as a means of payment offering new opportunities, but rather as a tool for strengthening the state.

Keywords

digital rouble, cryptocurrencies, basic human values

JEL codes: E71

Introduction

Definitions and principles of operation of digital currency

The digital rouble is a digital form of the Russian national currency that the Bank of Russia is planning to issue in addition to existing forms of money. It will represent a third form of the rouble along with cash and non-cash money. The digital rouble is a new pheno-

menon in the Russian economy, and so its acceptance by potential users is still poorly understood.

The Bank for International Settlements refers to digital currency as an asset that is stored electronically and can perform the same functions as physical currency, namely facilitating payment transactions (Bank for International Settlements 2020).

As for the digital currency development journey (Nejad 2016), two main directions are usually highlighted in the literature: cryptocurrency, with decentralised governance, and central bank digital currency, with centralised governance. The latter include the digital rouble, the attitude to which is the focus of this study. This study focuses on the expected behaviours of the digital rouble consumers once it is issued by the Central Bank of Russia. Although at first glance it may appear that there are few differences between centrally governed central bank digital currencies and cryptocurrencies, this is not the case. A Blockchain-based cryptocurrency is not controlled by governments or banks but is implemented on a fully decentralised platform independent of any government or central authority (Rajput et al. 2015).

Central bank digital currency (CBDC) is different from cryptocurrencies. It is an electronic liability issued by a central bank, which can be used for settlements and for storing value (Söilen and Benhayoun 2021). CBDC can be seen as a new form of electronic money supply, which in a sense already exists in the form of central bank reserves (Meaning et al. 2018).

Digital currency belongs to currencies that fulfil the following criteria (Emanuella 2021):

1. A central bank issues it in digital form.
2. Anyone has the right to own it. It is not a privilege held, for example, by credit institutions.
3. It is the same currency as central bank notes or deposits.
4. It can be used as a payment instrument in retail payments.
5. When two parties conduct a transaction, there is no third party – at least not a private one – to verify or execute the payment in the role of central counterparty. The same principle applies to banknote payments.

Studies and methodologies to explore attitudes towards digital currency and cryptocurrency

There is little research available on the associations between basic human values and digital currency use. However, some studies looked at the role of cultural differences in the use of digital currency. Hofstede's cultural values (individualism-collectivism, power distance, masculinity-femininity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation) were found to influence the use of blockchain-based currency (Salcedo and Gupta 2021). Moreover, collectivism, power distance, masculinity and long-term orientation have a positive association with it, while uncertainty avoidance, a negative one. It is also known from previous studies that cultural values play an important role in explaining how people respond to technology-mediated phenomena (Gupta et al. 2021). For example, a recent study highlights the role of individual-level values in explaining the extent to which people are willing to use sharing economy applications (e.g., Uber or Airbnb) for renting or leasing goods (Gupta et al. 2019). Therefore, research on the use of digital currency needs to consider people's interests.

People who share collectivist traits are more likely to use blockchain-based currency to make online purchases. These traits are, for example, shared collective success and trust

in others who are perceived to be similar. These traits are able to predict technology-mediated outcomes (Salcedo and Gupta 2021).

People from cultures with high power distance are more likely to use blockchain-based currency for online purchases. This is because people from high power-distance cultures are inspired by other individuals who are believed to have more power in society. Having knowledge of blockchain technology and even more so, owning and spending blockchain-based currency is likely to increase a person's status in a society with high power distance. Moreover, the endorsement of the use of blockchain-based currency by influential individuals in society may lead to others starting to use the currency (Salcedo and Gupta 2021).

The findings of other studies (Hoehle et al. 2015) indicate that people with high masculinity values will be willing to use technology or a technologically mediated service provided that its advantages are obvious. According to (Merkin et al. 2014), masculine cultures favour explicit (direct) over implicit (high-context) communication styles. Therefore, in order to encourage masculinity-oriented individuals to start using digital currency, it is important to first demonstrate the advantages of the technology to them.

Some studies have linked uncertainty avoidance values to people's ability to accept risk as opposed to their inclination to avoid risk (Hofstede et al. 2010; Yoo et al. 2011). Confidence in a new technology, especially if it is a new payment system that is not regulated by government or banks, may cause anxiety in people with high uncertainty avoidance values. Consequently, they may be less inclined to use digital currency, which is also supported by a study on the use of the blockchain technology, which corroborates a negative association between the degree of uncertainty avoidance and the use of blockchain currency (Salcedo and Gupta 2021).

Cultural values focused on the long term are associated with pragmatism and questioning existing norms, traditions, and rituals in order to invent and innovate for a sustainable future. Moving from the existing forms of payment systems to a financial system focused on digital currency will require a fundamental paradigm shift as well as a long-term orientation (Salcedo and Gupta 2021).

Another study shows that the values of Self-Enhancement, Security, and Openness to Change have an impact on participation in and use of digital instruments. Also, the same study demonstrates that the values also influence the way digital systems are used. It was found that people with higher values of Security tend to have shorter, goal-oriented interactions with the digital system, while people who are higher on the value of Openness to Change interact with the instruments more frequently (Palacin et al. 2021).

A Turkish case study (Bayrakdaroglu et al. 2018) did not directly examine the role of values, but focused on the motivations for using digital currency, using Bitcoin as an example. Experienced Bitcoin users were asked to describe why they were willing or not willing to use this digital currency. According to the findings, the willingness to use digital currency varies depending on different factors. Among the positive factors, practicality (75%), utility (50%), challenge (50%), curiosity (37.5%), competition (12.5%), and usability (12.5%) stood out. The most negative factor identified was the perceived control over the use of cryptocurrency, which makes it impossible to use these monetary units as much or in the way one would like.

A study was conducted in India of the local attitudes towards the use of India's digital rupee (Krishnan et al. 2023). The study examined the factors that might influence young people's intention to use digital currency. The most important factors were found to be perceived ease of use and perceived utility. Furthermore, these two factors influence how information about digital currency is disseminated, the transparency of its use, and the personal

and legal responsibilities associated with it. Ultimately, all these factors influence the level of trust in digital currency and the intention to use it in everyday life.

However, the above studies assessed various aspects of attitudes towards using digital currency abroad. Studies on the digital rouble have mainly focused on the economic and legal aspects of this phenomenon, paying less attention to how Russians, the end users, perceive the digital rouble. There is only limited research on Russians' opinions and perceptions of the digital rouble. Therefore, further research in this area could help to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how the Russian population perceives the digital rouble.

Basic human values and digital currency. Hypotheses of the study

Despite the staggering growth in the popularity of cryptocurrency and digital currency, we still have a poor understanding of the psychological processes behind it. In particular, what motivates people to switch to digital forms of money remains unclear. Since basic values motivate people to action, we suggest that they are associated with people's willingness to use digital currency in general and the digital rouble in particular.

Currently, there have been no research done on the associations between basic human values and the willingness to use state digital currency. There are studies that look at psychological characteristics of people and their ownership of or attitudes towards cryptocurrency; for example, the association between the dark triad traits and cryptocurrency ownership (Littrell et al. 2024). People with these traits are more likely to have risky financial preferences, high confidence in their decisions, and an interest in independent, decentralised forms of assets that provide a sense of freedom and control. For example, narcissism may contribute to increased confidence in one's ability to manage cryptocurrency; psychopathy, to risk tolerance; and Machiavellianism, to a strategic assessment of the prospects of cryptocurrency ownership with a view to achieving personal goals (Littrell et al. 2024). Narcissistic traits are associated with positive attitudes towards cryptocurrency, while Machiavellian traits correlate with the intention to buy cryptocurrency (Martin et al. 2022). There are literally few studies of the association between basic values and the attitudes towards cryptocurrency. The basic psychological mechanism that underlies such studies is that values influence attitudes, while attitudes, in turn, influence behaviour (Fisher 2017).

According to the Theory of Basic Human Values (Schwartz 2012), values are desired goals that people seek to achieve by satisfying a limited set of existential needs associated with their biological nature, co-ordinated action, and survival in groups. People in different situations and societies must find ways to fulfil these needs, which results in the shaping of a limited and universal set of values. The Refined Theory of Basic Human Values suggests 19 basic values, which are schematically charted within a circular structure depending on the orientation of these values. For example, universalism is on the opposite side of the circle relative to power, because the motivational goal of universalism is to protect the well-being of all people, while the motivational goal of power is to dominate people and resources. Similarly, conformism is on the opposite side of the circle relative to self-direction because the motivational goal of conformism is to restrain impulses that are likely to violate social expectations or norms, while the motivational goal of self-direction is independent thought.

The basic values can be grouped into four higher-order categories that reflect people's underlying motivational goals. These are Openness to Change, as opposed to Conservation, and Self-Enhancement, as opposed to Self-Transcendence. The former value opposition reflects the contradiction between the desire to challenge the status quo, which emphasises

autonomy, on the one hand, and the desire to preserve the status quo by engaging in traditional and safe activities, on the other hand. The latter value opposition reflects the contradiction between the seeking of personal well-being through power and focusing on one's own achievements, on the one hand, and the seeking of the well-being of others through charitable and altruistic activities and concern for the environment, on the other hand.

Figure 1 presents the Circular Motivational Continuum of basic human values according to S.H. Schwartz.

Figure 1. Circular Motivational Continuum of 19 Values (Schwartz et al. 2012)

The value oppositions described in the circle chart govern and motivate human behaviour (Schwartz 2012). This means that people act according to their motivational goals. For example, someone may decide to travel for a year with just a backpack because they are strongly committed to the values of stimulation and hedonism. Another person may choose to pursue a high-stress, high-reward career due to their strong preference for achievement and power.

Values are formed during early socialisation and continue to develop throughout life (Smallenbroek et al. 2023). Values can change depending on circumstances and social situation. For example, moving up (or down) the social ladder means that a person faces a different set of needs than before, and therefore has to adjust or revise his or her values.

Accordingly, when state digital currency emerges, we can expect that basic values will guide the behaviours associated with the use of the currency. What values could be important in this context?

We suggest that the potential for novelty and financial advantages offered by the digital rouble may be associated with the values of Openness to Change and Self-Enhancement. In particular, the emergence of cryptocurrency was linked to an innovative application of the blockchain technology, which is gradually changing the perception of money. People

who prefer motivational goals that involve trying new things and acting in ways that stimulate them may be motivated to use the digital rouble because of the changes in the financial system caused by the use of this digital currency. *Therefore, we suggest that Russians will positively associate the value category Openness to Change with various aspects of their willingness to use the digital rouble (hypothesis 1).*

We can also suggest that those people who strive for personal success, achievement, search for new resources for their achievements and power, i.e. those who are focused on the values of Self-Enhancement, can also consider the new type of digital currency as a source for satisfying these motivational goals. *We suggest accordingly that the value category Self-Enhancement in Russians will be positively associated with various aspects of their willingness to use the digital rouble (hypothesis 2).*

Also, we do not expect any association between the value categories Conservation and Self-Transcendence and Russians' willingness to use the digital rouble.

Methodology

The research was conducted online because the respondents needed to be active internet users, who could potentially use digital currency, including the digital rouble. The research was conducted on the anketolog.ru platform between 26 April and 5 May 2024. Participants completed the questionnaire remotely and were paid a small monetary reward for their response. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of the study's purpose.

Sample. A total of 300 respondents participated in the study residing in different regions of Russia. The age of respondents ranged from 18 to 67 years; the average age of the sample was 37.3 years. The sample was balanced by sex, with 150 men and 150 women included. Most of the respondents (83.6%) had either a higher education qualification (54.6%) or a secondary vocational qualification (29%). Eighteen per cent of respondents were unemployed, while 82 per cent were employed. The income levels of the employed respondents varied as follows: 29.6% had an income of less than 30,000 roubles per month; 43.1% had an income between 30,000 and 80,000 roubles per month; and 27.3% had an income of more than 80,000 roubles per month.

Toolkit. The study used two techniques.

1. Questionnaire 'Methodology of assessing attitudes towards the digital rouble'

We used a modified version of the questionnaire for assessing the acceptance of central bank digital currencies (CBDC) (Söilen and Benhayoun 2021). The original version of the questionnaire refers to central bank digital currency, while we replaced this wording with 'digital rouble'.

The original version of the methodology includes the following scales:

1. Performance expectancy – this parameter shows the extent to which using digital roubles will increase the efficiency and simplify the management of financial transactions.
2. Effort expectancy – this parameter shows how easy or difficult the respondent thinks it would be to master the digital currency system.
3. Facilitating conditions – the parameter shows the extent to which the state has created conditions for using digital currency, including infrastructure, training, and technical support.
4. Social influence – this parameter shows the extent to which a person relies on the opinions of significant others when using the state digital currency.

5. Trust in the currency system – the parameter shows how much the respondents trust the central bank and the state's entire digital currency system.
6. Behavioral intention – this parameter shows how actively the respondent intends to use digital rubles once they become available.
7. Intended behavior of use – statements of this scale allow us to assess the range of areas in which respondents plan to use the digital rouble.

The level of agreement with the questionnaire statements was to be rated on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Each of the seven parameters was assessed using three or four questions. The digital rouble assessment methodology, along with the wording of the questions, is explained in the annex to this paper. This methodology demonstrates good validity and reliability (Tatarko et al. in press).

2. S.H. Schwartz's values methodology. When analysing values, we used a new Russian version of the S.H. Schwartz's values questionnaire (Schwartz et al. 2012), which includes 57 questions to measure 19 individual values (PVQ-R). Respondents were asked to rate how similar they were to the person described in each question on a six-point scale ranging from 'not at all like me' to 'very similar to me'. The average for each of the 19 values was then calculated using the key. Then, for further analysis, we combined individual values into the value categories Conservation, Openness to Change, Self-Transcendence, and Self-Enhancement.

Data Processing. Multiple regression analysis was used to process the data because both the dependent and predictor variables were derived from averaging, and the scales varied across a wide range. Therefore, for example, ordinal regression was impossible to use. When building regression models, all the values were included in the model at the same time because, according to S.H. Schwartz, they represent a single motivational continuum and are therefore to be used in all calculations simultaneously.

Findings

During the analysis, we examined the associations between each value category and each scale of the methodology used to assess attitudes towards the digital rouble. Table 1 presents a hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the 'Performance expectancy scale.

As can be seen in Table 1, age is negatively associated with the expectation that using the digital rouble will make financial transactions more efficient and easier to manage. Among the higher-order values, those of 'Self-Transcendence' are positively associated with the expectation of higher efficiency from using the digital rouble.

No association between the higher-order values and the 'Effort expectancy' scale was found (Table 2).

As can be seen in Table 3, sex and age are positively associated with the 'Facilitating conditions' scale among the control variables. There is also a positive association between this scale and the value category 'Self-Enhancement'.

Furthermore, we examined the association between the higher-order values and the 'Social influence' scale, which indicates the extent to which a person is influenced by influential referents' opinions regarding the use of the state digital currency. As can be seen in Table 4, the socio-demographic indicators of the respondents were not a factor in this case. Of the values examined, 'Self-Transcendence' and 'Self-Enhancement' had a positive effect, while 'Openness to Change' had a negative effect.

Table 1. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the ‘Performance expectancy’ scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	B	SE
Socio-demographic indicators				
Sex	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.11
Age	-0.15*	0.01	-0.14*	0.01
Education	0.11	0.03	0.10	0.03
Income	0.08	0.02	0.06	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.17*	0.12
Openness to Change			0.006	0.13
Conservation			0.02	0.24
Self-Enhancement			0.07	0.09
R ²	0.042		0.091	
F	3.06*		3.98***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the p < 0.001 level. *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05.

Table 2. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the ‘Effort expectancy’ scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic indicators				
Sex	0.02	0.11	0.01	0.11
Age	0.001	0.005	0.04	0.005
Education	0.11	0.03	0.09	0.03
Income	0.07	0.02	0.03	0.03
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.14	0.12
Openness to Change			0.09	0.13
Conservation			0.11	0.09
Self-Enhancement			0.06	0.08
R ²	0.023		0.104	
F	1.65		4.80***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of p < 0.001. *** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05.

Table 3. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the 'Facilitating conditions' scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Sex	0.13*	0.10	0.12*	0.09
Age	0.08	0.004	0.12*	0.004
Education	-0.05	0.02	-0.07	0.02
Income	0.11	0.02	0.07	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.16	0.10
Openness to Change			0.02	0.11
Conservation			-0.19	0.20
Self-Enhancement			0.20**	0.78
R ²	0.026		0.129	
F	1.97		5.15***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the 'Social influence scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Sex	0.04	0.13	0.04	0.12
Age	-0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01
Education	-0.03	0.03	-0.01	0.03
Income	-0.08	0.03	-0.10	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.30***	0.13
Openness to Change			-0.34***	0.14
Conservation			-0.038	0.09
Self-Enhancement			0.35***	0.10
R ²	0.011		0.135	
F	0.76		5.43***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Table 5. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the ‘Trust in the Currency System’ scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Sex	0.09	0.11	0.09	0.11
Age	-0.07	0.01	-0.06	0.01
Education	-0.10	0.03	-0.09	0.03
Income	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.27***	0.11
Openness to Change			-0.16	0.12
Conservation			0.10	0.08
Self-Enhancement			0.11	0.09
R ²	0.020		0.105	
F	1.46		4.05***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Table 6. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the ‘Behavioural Intention’ scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Sex	-0.03	0.11	-0.04	0.11
Age	-0.10	0.01	-0.06	0.01
Education	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03
Income	0.10	0.02	0.07	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.15	0.11
Openness to Change			-0.02	0.12
Conservation			0.09	0.08
Self-Enhancement			0.12	0.09
R ²	0.022		0.09	
F	1.60		4.13***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

A similar pattern emerges when we consider the association between the values and the ‘Trust in the Currency System’ scale (Table 5). Again, socio-demographic indicators of the respondents were not a factor. Of the values examined, ‘Self-Transcendence’ showed a positive effect.

A hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the higher-order values and the ‘Behavioural Intention’ scale in Table 6 shows the extent to which respondents intend to actively use the digital rouble once it becomes available. It can be seen that this indicator is not statistically significantly associated with the socio-demographic indicators. No statistically significant associations with the values were found either.

Table 7. Hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the values and the ‘Intended behavior of use’ scale

Predictor	Model 1		Model 2	
	β	SE	β	SE
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Sex	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.10
Age	-0.12*	0.01	-0.10	0.01
Education	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03
Income	0.11	0.02	0.08	0.02
Higher-order values				
Self-Transcendence			0.24**	0.11
Openness to Change			-0.08	0.12
Conservation			0.11	0.08
Self-Enhancement			0.12	0.09
R ²	0.028		0.126	
F	2.04		5.02***	

Note: The variation of R² is statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.001$. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

A hierarchical linear analysis of the association between the higher-order values and the ‘Intended behavior of use’ scale in Table 7 reveals the extent to which respondents intend to actively use the digital rouble once it becomes available. It can be seen that this indicator is only negatively associated with respondents’ age. Of the values examined, ‘Self-Transcendence’ had a positive and statistically significant effect.

Discussion

Table 8 provides a consolidated view of the resulting associations to make the identified trends easier to see.

Overall, we find that our results do not fully align with those of a similar study conducted in Germany (Stanciu et al. 2024). In the above study, Self-Enhancement values were positively associated with the desire to own and positive attitudes towards cryptocurrency. In our

study, Self-Enhancement values were also associated with the scales characterising digital rouble acceptance, but to a much lesser extent than Self-Transcendence values. Additionally, the ‘Openness to Change’ values were negatively associated with the ‘Social influence’ scale (the extent to which a person is influenced by significant referents’ opinions regarding the use of state digital currency). In other words, people in Russia who are open to change do not perceive the state digital currency as empowering but rather resist the social impact that supports this kind of currency.

Table 8. Consolidation of identified relationships

		Self-Transcendence	Self-Enhancement		
SOCIAL FOCUS	(+)	‘Performance expectancy’	(+)	‘Facilitating conditions’	PERSONAL FOCUS
	(+)	‘Social influence’	(+)	‘Social influence’	
	(+)	‘Trust in the currency system’			
	(+)	‘Intended behavior of use’			
		Conservation	Openness to Change		
			(-)	‘Social influence’	

Therefore, the values of personal focus, which underlie individual aspirations for achievement, comfortable life, and self-actualisation, show positive associations with various indicators of the willingness to use the digital rouble.

As for the social-focus values of ‘Self-Transcendence’ and ‘Conservation’, opposite trends are observed. Values of ‘Self-Transcendence’ are positively linked to four of the seven scales used to assess attitudes towards the digital rouble (see Table 8). This suggests that people with these values are more likely to accept and use the digital rouble. In contrast, we found no statistically significant associations with the ‘Conservation’ values, as we had suggested.

Accordingly, we can conclude that our hypotheses were partially corroborated. Indeed, the ‘Self-Enhancement’ values were to some extent associated with the willingness to use the digital rouble. However, the role of ‘Self-Transcendence’ values was much stronger than we suggested. It was the ‘Self-Transcendence’ values that were associated with most of the digital rouble acceptance scales. There are three possible explanations for these findings.

1) Attitudes towards state digital currency differ somewhat from those towards cryptocurrency, reflecting different values. Previous studies have examined attitudes towards cryptocurrency. As cryptocurrency is not issued by the state, individual values and motivations behind the willingness to use state digital currency and cryptocurrency not issued by the state may differ.

2) The association between values and attitudes towards digital products in Russia is culturally specific. Studies indicate that the same values may have different effects in different cultures rather than being universal. For instance, values are differently associated with attitudes towards immigrants in different countries (Ponizovskiy 2016) or subjective well-being (Messner 2023). Universalism, for instance, is more strongly associated with positive attitudes towards immigrants in Western democracies than in post-communist Eastern European countries (Ponizovskiy 2016). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that, in many Western countries, ‘Tradition’ values are negatively associated with subjective well-being

(Sortheix and Schwartz 2017), whereas in other regions, these values foster the development of a positive identity, the intergenerational transfer of adaptive practices and the maintaining of cultural stability, thereby enhancing subjective well-being (Messner 2023). Cultural context is also important. In particular, the Human Development Index can moderate and weaken the negative association between the values of Tradition and subjective well-being (Sortheix and Schwartz 2017).

Similarly, we suggest that values may affect attitudes towards digital currency in Russia in a different way than in Germany due to Russia's specific cultural context, which requires further exploration. One such moderator could be the low level of institutional trust among Russians.

3) Perhaps state digital currency is perceived not so much as a means of payment offering new opportunities, but rather as a means of additional state control. Therefore, we see that the 'Openness to Change' values show a negative association with the 'Social influence' scale of the digital rouble acceptance methodology.

Overall, it seems that Russians do not see the digital rouble as a means of harnessing new technological opportunities, but rather as the state's attempt to streamline financial processes and impose discipline on society. It is evident to anyone that the introduction of the digital rouble will make theft and illegal money transfers more difficult.

At the moment, it is likely that Russians do not understand the personal benefits of state digital currency, apart from the possibility of strengthening state controls over financial processes in Russia.

Findings

1. Russians' acceptance of the digital rouble is positively associated with higher-order values such as 'Self-Transcendence' and 'Self-Enhancement', while negative associations have been found with 'Openness to Change'.
2. Based on previous research, we can conclude that the logic behind the association between the values and acceptance of the state-issued digital rouble differs compared with that of cryptocurrency created by non-state entities.
3. The findings suggest that, at present, Russians do not see the digital rouble as a means of payment offering new opportunities, but rather as a way for the state to consolidate its power.

Conclusion

In the present study, we examined the association between Russians' four basic higher-order values and their attitudes towards the digital rouble. The findings differed from the original hypotheses. We believe that further research into Russians is required to examine the associations between values and attitudes not only towards the digital rouble, but also towards cryptocurrency per se. Similar comparative cultural research in other countries is also required to check the findings for universality and to determine whether the associations between values and attitudes towards state- and non-state digital currency differ in different countries. Further research into the associations between values and attitudes towards the digital rouble in Russia is required to evaluate the robustness of these findings, particularly given that Russian attitudes towards the digital rouble are likely to change over time.

The main limitation of this study is that the sample size was relatively small (300 respondents) and unrepresentative, as all respondents were recruited through an online panel.

An important aspect of future research is to consider contextual cultural factors that may mediate or moderate the association between values and attitudes towards digital currency. Such research would clarify which socio-cultural factors may offset or modify the theoretically expected effects of values on different aspects of attitudes towards state currency or cryptocurrency.

References

- Bank for International Settlements (2020) Central bank digital currencies: foundational principles and core features. URL: <https://www.bis.org/publ/othp33.htm>.
- Bayraktaroğlu F, Bayraktaroğlu A, Bulut ZA (2018) Virtual Currency Usage in Digital Economy: Attitudes Concerning Bitcoin. 2nd International Conference on New Approaches in Social Sciences and Humanities, Istanbul.
- Emanuella CS (2021) Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) Sebagai Alat Pembayaran di Indonesia. *Jurist-Diction* 4(6): 2243-2276. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jd.v4i6.31845>.
- Fisher R (2017) From Values to Behavior and from Behavior to Values. In: Roccas S, Sagiv L (Eds) *Values and Behavior*. Springer, Cham, 219-235. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56352-7_10.
- Gupta M, Esmaeilzadeh P, Uz I, Tennant VM (2019) The effects of national cultural values on individuals' intention to participate in peer-to-peer sharing economy. *Journal of Business Research* 97: 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.12.018>.
- Gupta M, Shoja A, Mikalef P (2021) Toward the understanding of national culture in the success of non-pharmaceutical technological interventions in mitigating COVID-19 pandemic. *Annals of Operations Research* 319: 1433-1450. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-021-03962-z>.
- Hoehle H, Zhang X, Venkatesh V (2015) An espoused cultural perspective to understand continued intention to use mobile applications: A four-country study of mobile social media application usability. *European Journal of Information Systems* 24(3): 337–359. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2014.43>.
- Hofstede G, Hofstede GJ, Minkov M (2010) *Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind* (3rd ed.). McGraw Hill Professional, 561 pp.
- Krishnan R, Kandasamy L, Perumal E, Mariyappan MS, Sankar Ganesh K, Govindaraj M, Malali AB (2023) Youth Intention Towards Implementing Digital Currency: Role of Social Media and Government. In: Chavadi C, Thangam D (Eds) *Global Perspectives on Social Media Usage Within Governments*. IGI Global Scientific Publishing, 276-296.
- Littrell S, Klofstad C, Uscinski JE (2024) The political, psychological, and social correlates of cryptocurrency ownership. *PLOS ONE* 19(7): e0305178. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0305178>.
- Martin BAS, Chrysochou P, Strong C, Wang D, Yao J (2022) Dark personalities and bitcoin: The influence of the dark tetrad on cryptocurrency attitude and buying intention. *Personality and Individual Differences* 188: 111453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111453>.
- Meaning J, Dyson B, Barker J, Clayton E (2018) Broadening Narrow Money: Monetary Policy with a Central Bank Digital Currency. Bank of England Working Paper No. 724.
- Merkin R, Taras V, Steel P (2014) State of the art themes in cross-cultural communication research: A systematic and meta-analytic review. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations* 38: 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2013.10.004>.

- Messner W (2023) Being happy: The role of personal value priorities in subjective well-being across European countries. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management* 23(2): 389-421. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14705958231180049>.
- Nejad MG (2016) Research on Financial Services Innovations: A Quantitative Review and Future Research Directions. *International Journal of Bank Marketing* 34(7): 1042-1068. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-08-2015-0129>.
- Palacin V, Ferrario MA, Hsieh G, Knutas A, Wolff A, Porras J (2021) Human values and digital citizen science interactions. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 149: 102605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2021.102605>.
- Ponizovskiy V (2016) Values and attitudes towards immigrants: Cross-cultural differences across 25 countries. *Psychology. Journal of the Higher School of Economics* 13(2): 256-272. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1813-8918-2016-2-256-272>.
- Rajput U, Abbas F, Hussain R, Eun H, Oh H (2015) A simple yet efficient approach to combat transaction malleability in Bitcoin. In: Rhee KH, Yi J (Eds) *Information Security Applications*. WISA 2014. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Springer, Cham, 27-37. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-15087-1_3.
- Salcedo E, Gupta M (2021) The effects of individual-level espoused national cultural values on the willingness to use Bitcoin-like blockchain currencies. *International Journal of Information Management* 60: 102388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102388>.
- Schwartz SH (2012) An overview of the Schwartz theory of basic values. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture* 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1116>.
- Schwartz S, Butenko TP, Sedova DS, Lipatova AS (2012) A Refined theory of basic personal values: validation in Russia. *Psychology. Journal of Higher School of Economics* 9(2): 43-70 (In Russian).
- Smallenbroek O, Stanciu A, Arant R, Boehnke K (2023) Are values stable throughout adulthood? Evidence from two German long-term panel studies. *PLOS ONE* 18(11): e0289487. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0289487>.
- Söilen KS, Benhayoun L (2021) Household acceptance of central bank digital currency: The role of institutional trust. *International Journal of Bank Marketing* 40(1): 172-196. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-04-2021-0156>.
- Sortheix FM, Schwartz SH (2017) Values that underlie and undermine well-being: Variability across countries. *European Journal of Personality* 31(2): 187-201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2096>.
- Stanciu A, Partsch M, Lechner CM (2024) Basic human values and the adoption of cryptocurrency. *Frontiers in Psychology* 15: 1395674. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1395674>
- Tatarko AN, Rodionov GYa, Nikolaeva KI (in press) Razrabotka metodiki 'Ocenka prinyatiya cifrovogo rublya' (OPCR) [Development of the methodology 'Assessment of Digital Rouble Acceptance (ADA)']. *Social'naya psihologiya i obshchestvo*.
- Yoo B, Donthu N, Lenartowicz T (2011) Measuring Hofstede's five dimensions of cultural values at the individual level: Development and validation of CVSCALE. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing* 23(3-4): 193-210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08961530.2011.578059>.

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Annex

You will be presented with several statements about the use of the digital rouble. Please read them and indicate the extent to which you agree with each one. Use the following five-point scale: 1 – absolutely disagree; 2 – disagree; 3 – don't know/not sure; 4 – agree; 5 – absolutely agree.

Table A1. The digital rouble acceptance methodology

Statements	Scale				
1. Using the digital rouble should increase my personal productivity, for example by saving time.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Using the digital rouble should enable me to process financial transactions faster.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Using the digital rouble should make managing my financial transactions more efficient.	1	2	3	4	5
4. I need to learn fast how to use the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
5. I need to quickly become proficient in using the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
6. I need to be able to use the digital rouble easily for my own purposes.	1	2	3	4	5
7. Using the digital rouble will require me to learn something new.	1	2	3	4	5
8. Using the digital rouble will require high levels of compatibility with the other technologies I use.	1	2	3	4	5
9. Using the digital rouble will require the ability to quickly access support from others, such as a helpdesk or knowledgeable acquaintances, in case difficulties arise.	1	2	3	4	5
10. The people who matter to me should advise me to use the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
11. The people who have influence over me should advise me to use the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
12. The people whose opinion matters to me should advise me to use the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
13. I trust the central bank more than commercial banks to pay me my wages/ salary using the digital rouble.	1	2	3	4	5
14. I would trust the central bank more than a commercial bank with managing my digital wallet.	1	2	3	4	5

Statements	Scale				
15. I have more confidence in a state-controlled digital currency system than in one that is not (Bitcoin, for example, is uncontrolled).	1	2	3	4	5
16. I'm going to use the digital rouble all the time when it becomes available.	1	2	3	4	5
17. I'm definitely going to try using the digital rouble when it becomes available.	1	2	3	4	5
18. I am going to use the digital rouble for online purchases.	1	2	3	4	5
19. I am going to use the digital rouble to make transfers to friends, relatives, etc.	1	2	3	4	5
20. I am going to use the digital rouble to get paid for services apart from my main job.	1	2	3	4	5

Data processing involved calculation of the mean values for each of the seven scales according to the keys. All questions are direct.

Keys:

1. Performance expectancy (1, 2, 3).
2. Effort expectancy (4, 5, 6).
3. Facilitating conditions (7, 8, 9).
4. Social influence (10, 11, 12).
5. Trust in the currency system (13, 14, 15).
6. Behavioural intention (16, 17).
7. Intended behavior of use (18, 19, 20).